

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

EBT Cover Letter for **comment** submissions

Version 8 Dec 2025

0. Instructions for users

Users should download this form as a Word document, complete it, and upload it as a cover letter as part of their manuscript submission package. Note that these instructions can be deleted from the submitted version of the cover letter.

In some circumstances, particularly if an Expert Commentary presents novel data, code, or has other characteristics that necessitate more comprehensive reporting of data, we may ask for additional information to be declared or referenced.

1. Submission data. All items are mandatory, please complete as indicated.

2. Minimum information checklist. All items are mandatory, please confirm their presence in the manuscript. Box 2.6 can be checked even if no third party data or code are used.

3. Index of supplemental materials. Supplemental materials should be given descriptive file names that allow easy identification of contents (e.g. “Raw Data” rather than “Supplemental Materials 1”). “Ref” is for reference number, to make it simple to refer to individual files.

1. Submission data

1.1	Name of corresponding author	Carrie Price
1.2	Email address of corresponding author	carrieprice@pm.me ; cprice@toxstrategies.com
1.3	DOI of manuscript preprint	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19052550
1.4	Title of manuscript	Advocating for the Role of Library and Information Specialists in Evidence-Based Toxicology

1.5	Confirmation of reading EBT's Instructions for Authors	Yes
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2. Minimum information checklist

We confirm that we have provided the following information:

Key: Y = Provided | N = Not Available | D = Does Not Apply

Ref	Y/N	Item
2.1	Y	Full name, affiliations, and ORCID(s) (if available) of each author
2.2	Y	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement (Tenzing may be helpful)
2.3	D	Complete funding details
2.4	Y	A fully-informative disclosure of interests for all authors (suggested template)
2.5	D	3rd-party data and program code are fully cited (data standard: TOP 1, level 3)
2.6	Author comments for the editor: None	

We ask for a **CRediT statement** (item 2.2) to support making it easier to find and share information about author contributions. Authors may find the [Tenzing app](#) useful for CRediT statements (please remember to cite it, as per item 2.6). For **disclosures of interest**, we request both financial and non-financial interests to be declared; authors may find [this DOI template](#) helpful. For 3rd party data and code, we seek to comply with TOP data standards (specifically Top 1, Level 3: [click here for more information](#)).

3. Index of supplemental materials

We have provided the following supplemental materials alongside our Working Paper:

Ref.	Title	Notes (if applicable)
	n/a	
	[add rows as needed]	